

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: JANNEH****FIRST NAME: MAIMUNA****PROGRAM CODE: MSDD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA**

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did *not* use Grammarly Premium (uses free version)

The author used the following software: MSWord 2007 on Windows 10

DILEMMA IN WRITING ACCEPTABLE ENGLISH

1) INTRODUCTION

Response Papers are required for Master's in Sustainable Development and Diplomacy (MSDD) at Euclid University upon reading assigned materials or periods. Thus, a coursepack on writing skills was the first to be assigned which I have read and noticed that English writing rules are confusing and inconsistent. Moreover, I realized that my English teacher did not thoroughly explain why the different styles in writing.

The study material, which is in Portable Document Format (PDF) and has 83 pages, helps students to get the basics of writing to become professional writers. The e-book covers a range of significant topics detailing the features of a good essay; planning and researching; error checking; writing guidelines; rules to abide by; formatting and referencing methods; plagiarism and its implications; among other useful tips on academic and professional writing.

This paper discussed topics that I found interesting and educative, but yet confusing.

2) A GREAT DEAL OF CONFUSION

Having the coursepack for period one, I asked myself this question: "Is it really easy to write acceptable English, especially as a non-native speaker"? From this book, I realized I have been making many errors in writing. The initial notion was that the difference between the US and UK styles of writing was the spelling convention. I was proofed wrong. Probably my English teachers owed me an explanation. Their teaching

method encouraged me to memorize the spelling instead of understanding why the difference in spelling the same word with the same meaning.

A computer that is set to US English dictionary would underscore UK spellings as incorrect; and vice versa.

I was taught while learning to type that two spaces are types after a period and one space after a comma. However, I learned from this book that convention was because of the fixed nature of typewriter fonts. It was reasoned that with the advent of computers, spaces are flexible. When a document is justified it creates extra space; hence one space is enough to create after a period (EUCLID 2015, 47).

Proper use of possessive or contraction cases also confuses. I understand the difference and I usually use them properly. What baffles me is why native English speakers use them wrongly? I observed the errors from my interaction with some native speakers who I “instant message” Additionally, even some of my fellow Gambians who were expected to be professional writers made such mistakes. What causes the confusion, teachers or the language?

Notwithstanding, I am grateful that the ACA-401 coursepack tremendously improved my writing skills as it clarified the difference between American and British styles of writing. This resulted in immediate corrections in my writing skills. I used both styles without knowing.

One example of a spelling difference is “Realize” (US) and “Realise” (UK). America uses “z” in the spelling and Britain uses “s”. What was not clear to me was the root of the different spellings.

It is difficult to be consistent with a style when one knows not all the differences. Probably you might find inconsistency in this write-up. Due to the effects of colonization, I mostly use British spelling even whereas the computer (set to US English) underlines it as an error. Funnily, although I initially thought that the Gambia was influenced by British English, I learned from this lesson that America says “Public Holiday” while Britain uses the expression “Bank Holiday” (EUCLID 2015, 56). In the Gambia, we commonly use the expression “Public Holiday” or “Holiday” which is American style. I assumed Bank Holiday to have been an off-day for Bankers; and Boxing Day a day for boxing. Well, I felt stupid to have thought that way.

It is optional to use oxford comma [comma before the conjunction “and” in a list of items], but not using it either can cause confusion and misinterpretation of the context (EUCLID 2015, 48).

Another confusing bit is the date formats. Given these examples, 08/07/60 vs 08.07.60 or 080760, it would not be easy to tell whether it is August 7 or July 7. The standard ISO 8601 format is 2008-09-15 (EUCLID 2015, 59). In the Gambia civil service, the format is day/month/year. Going by that can lead to wrong interpretations of the cited formats.

Rule on the use of articles places the article “a” before a consonant and article “an” before a vowel. Applying this rule without exception would sound awkward in some cases because some words begin with a consonant but sound like a vowel. I understand from the lesson that sound takes precedence over the letter. If the word sounds like a vowel the article “an” is used, and if it sounds like a consonant the article “a” is used (EUCLID 2015, 49). For example, “An umbrella” instead of “A umbrella.”

The use of “I” or “me” is sometimes difficult as well. It is a common mistake to misuse the subject and the object forms (EUCLID 2015, 50).

a) US and UK Styles of Writing

Some examples are Defense vs Defence; License vs Licence; Cheque vs Check; Alright vs All right; Ageing vs Aging; Maths vs Math; and Honour vs Honor (EUCLID 2015, 54). Despite my influence by UK spelling, in my view, US spelling is easier because it spells words as pronounced. However, I was taught that an “s” between two vowels is pronounced as “z.” So that seems to justify the UK spelling.

b) Use of Punctuation Marks

The US put punctuation marks inside the quotation while the UK places them after the quotation mark. I discovered that I had the wrong knowledge about the use of a full stop in honorifics. I thought since honorifics are truncated, the full stop should be typed after it. Never knew I that the mere difference was US and UK preferences. That is “Mr.,” “Mrs.,” “Ms.,” and “Pr.” being US-style and “Mr,” “Mrs,” “Ms,” and “Pr” UK (EUCLID 2015, 48, 55).

i) *Apostrophe*

Contrary to what I was taught about possessive cases which says possessive nouns ending in “s” only add an apostrophe, and nouns not ending in “s” add “ ’s ”, the rule in this lesson says any possessive singular noun takes “ ’s “. This means even if the noun ends in “s” add “ ’s “, and any possessive plural noun adds “ ’s.” For example, Louis’s; Carlos’s (EUCLID 2015, 47).

On the other hand, the name Louis pronounced as loo-is or loo-ie becomes Louis’s and Louis’ in possessive cases. The rule indeed confuses writers.

ii) *Quotation Marks*

The American rule of quotation says all punctuation marks should be put inside the quotation. Conversely, punctuation is placed after the quotation mark in the British style.

The UK uses inverted commas for quotes while the US uses quotation marks. For verbatim quotes inside a quotation, the US uses quotation marks and the UK does the opposite. For example, “He shouted, ‘call me back!’ and then hang up.” -the US; ‘he shouted, “call me back!” and then hang up’. –the UK (EUCLID 2015, 48).

3) CONCLUSION

From the points outlined in this paper, I believed that it is indeed difficult to write acceptable English, especially as a non-native speaker due to contradicting rules, and conflicting preferences between the US vs UK English.

Despite this, I have benefited greatly from the basics this lesson taught me and I instantaneously apply the skills at work. On that note, I am grateful to the course instructor and coordinators for their patience and swift responses to my requests for assistance. The study material is humbling as it taught me that learning is an on-going process and has no age limit. It is good to test or refresh knowledge about the basics of any undertaking. The material though designed for high school students is equally useful for professionals.

REFERENCES

EUCLID. 2015. *ACA-401 Coursepack: Period 1*. Washington DC: Euclid University Press.

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